

Preliminary Study on National Road Condition of Ambon City, Indonesia

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Abstract

The national road in Ambon City connects Pattimura Airport with Yos Sudarso Port having double access with parallel road conditions. Some road segments are not continuous like Jalan A.M. Sangadji and Jalan Rijali, have two lanes but are still one-way. This study aims to review the capacity of the two national road segments in Ambon City based on the existence of each road section according to LHR conditions, side friction, and continuous road requirements. According to the scientific stages, the study was carried out in a structured and systematic manner using data from field observations and the latest secondary data from data sources in the BPJN XVI Ambon work unit covering Down Road and Upper Road). The study results were selected three alternative national road access. The first alternative, using down national road access with recommendations for reclamation of the Pantai Mardika road section, connecting six roads each: Yos Sudarso, Pala, Pantai Mardika, Pantai Batu Merah, Ongko Liong, and Jalan Sultan Hasanuddin. The second alternative uses upper national road access with recommendations for flyover development, connecting six roads: Pelabuhan, A.M. Sangadji, Diponegoro, Ahmad Yani, Rijali, and Sudirman. The Third alternative, using parallel national road access between down and upper national road for current conditions, with recommendations on traffic engineering and handling of several road sections to be continuous.

Keywords: *National road; Ambon City; existing conditions; segment; roads*

1. Introduction

Road access is an important infrastructure in supporting national development that connects growth centers between regions and national levels [1]. Therefore, increasing the quantity, quality, and efficiency of roads needs to be assessed at all times to improve public services. In line with this, stakeholders related to national roads play an important role in road function in optimizing, especially national ways [2].

Indonesia government regulation no. 34/2006 concerning roads [3] in article 7 states that the primary road network system is based on a spatial plan and service distribution of goods and services for the development of all regions at the national level. Aims to connect all distribution service nodes in the form of activity centers as follows: a) continually link national activity centers, regional activity centers, local activity centers to the center of environmental activities; and b) connecting between national centers of activity.

Based on the grouping of road functions, national roads are arterial and collector roads in the primary road network system that connects provincial capitals, national strategic

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ways, and toll roads [3]. The national strategic road referred to, is the path that connects the entrance of an area such as a road that connects the airport (Airport) with another airport. It can also be a road that connects the airport with the port in an area, such as the one in Ambon City today. The national highway in Ambon City connecting Pattimura Airport with Yos Sudarso Port has double access [4]. The national road in Ambon City corresponds to the Maluku provincial, national road network, consisting of two road segments with parallel conditions as follows (the sketch in Figure 1). Segment I, includes: *Yos Sudarso road- Pala road - Pantai Mardika road - Pantai Batu Merah road – Sultan Hasanuddin road*, hereinafter referred to as Down Road Segment. While segment II, includes *Pelabuhan road- A.M Sangadji road - Diponegoro road - Ahmad Yani road - Rijali road – Sudirman road*, hereinafter referred to as the Upper Road Segment.

Based on the existing conditions, several national roads that are not continuous, such as in *A.M Sangadji*, some roads have two lanes and one direction [4]. Thus some national roads are still occupied by parking vehicles. The effect of parking on a road body is a traffic problem that must be resolved because it causes a reduction in inadequate traffic lanes [5]. Parking also disrupts traffic flow, especially during rush hour in the parking area [6]. Therefore, a study of the existing condition of national roads in Ambon City is needed to produce several alternative recommendations for road use, as an effort to improve road performance.

This paper is intended to overview the national road condition in Ambon City to become a choice for the national road segment, along with supporting recommendations that are suitable to be submitted as national road access. The objective of the study is to review the two national road segment's capacity in Ambon City based on road section according to average daily traffic (LHR) conditions, side barriers, and continuous road requirements.

Figure 1. Existing Ambon City National Road

2. Theoretical Review

2.1. Indonesia National Road

According to Government Regulation No. 34/2006, the grouping of roads is intended to realize legal certainty over the administration of roads following the central government and regional governments. Public roads are classified according to their status as National Roads, Provincial Roads, Regency Roads, City Roads, and Village Roads. The road network grouping in Indonesia consists of:

1. National Road is an arterial road and collector road in the primary road network system that connects provincial capitals, national strategic roads, and toll roads.
2. Provincial Road is a collector road in the primary road network system that connects the provincial capital with the regency/city capital, or between the regency/city capital, and the provincial strategic road.
3. Regency Road is a local primary road network system that connects district capital with sub-district capital. There is sub-district capital, district capital with local activity center between local activity centers, public roads in the secondary road network system in the district area, and roads strategic district.
4. City Road is a public road in the secondary road network system that connects between service centers within the city, connects service centers with parcels, connects between parcels, and connects between residential centers in the town.
5. Village Road is a public road that connects the area and between settlements within the village and the environmental road.

2.2. Road Capacity

According to Government Regulation No. 34/2006 concerning Road article 12 paragraph (1), the road capacity is the maximum number of vehicles that can cross-specific cross-sections on each road segment, time units, road conditions, and accurate traffic. Capacity is defined as the maximum current that passes through a point on the freeway that can be maintained hour unit under the prevailing conditions. For an undivided highway, capacity is the maximum two-way current (a combination of both directions), for a freeway divided capacity is the maximum lane. Capacity values have been observed by collecting field data to the extent possible.

The lack of locations where traffic flows close to the freeway clean-ways capacity itself (not the capacity of intersections along the freeway), capacity has also been theoretically estimated assuming a mathematical relationship between density, speed, and flow [7]. Capacity is stated in passenger car units (SMP) as Equation [8], [9].

$$C = C_0 > FC_w \times FC_{SP} \text{ (smp/j) } \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: C = Capacity; C_0 = Basic capacity; FC_w = Freeway width adjustment factor; and FC_{SP} = Direction separation adjustment factor (only for highways).

2.3. Average Daily Traffic (LHR)

Average daily traffic abbreviated as LHR is a two-way traffic volume that passes through an average point in one day, usually calculated throughout the year. LHR is a standard term used in calculating traffic loads on a road segment and is the basis in the transportation planning process or the measurement of pollution caused by traffic flows on a road segment. Traffic volume for geometric road planning includes: 1) annual average daily traffic volume of the plan, calculated based on the current average daily traffic according to plan age and traffic growth factors; and 2) planning hour traffic volume, calculated based on average daily traffic volume. The k factor and

the traffic growth factor referred to are determined by the road operator based on the traffic growth conditions. Determination of the plan hour volume can be calculated using Equation 2.

$$Q_{\text{Jam Maks.}} = \text{LHR} \times k \times \text{PHF} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where: Q_{max} = Plan hour or maximum volume; LHR = average daily traffic k = conversion factor; and PHF = peak hour factor.

The k value according to Indonesian road capacity manual (MKJI) 1997 is a conversion factor if only the average daily traffic is known without the traffic distribution being known at every hour, the estimated value is influenced by the type of city and road [10]–[13] as in Table 1.

Table 1. Factors k According to the Indonesian Road Capacity Manual

City and Road Types	Percent Factor k
Cities with a population of > 1 million	
- Roads on commercial areas and arterial roads	7-8%
- Road in residential areas	8-9%
Cities with a population of 1 million	
- Roads in commercial areas and arterial roads	8-10%
- Road in residential areas	9-12%

2.4. Delays and Side Barriers

According to Indonesian Road Capacity Manual (MKJI) [11]–[13], delays are the additional travel time required to cross the road when compared to a crossing without going through an intersection. Delays at an intersection can occur for two reasons: a) traffic delays (DT) due to traffic interactions with other movements at an intersection; and b) geometric delays (DG) due to slowing and acceleration when turning at an intersection and stopping due to a traffic light.

Side barriers are the effects of activities beside road segments on traffic performance, for example, pedestrians (weight = 0.6) stopping public vehicles or other vehicles (weight = 0.8), cars entering and leaving land beside the road (weight = 1.0) and slow vehicles (weight = 0.4). Classification of side barriers can be seen under the following Table 2.

Table 2. Factors k According to the Indonesian Road Capacity Manual

Side Barriers Class	Code	Weighted Frequency and Occurrence (Both Sides)	Typical Conditions
Very low	VL	<50	Rural, agricultural, or underdeveloped
Low	L	50-100	Rural, some road side buildings
Medium	M	150-250	Village, settlement activities
High	H	250-350	Village, some market activities
Very High	VH	>350	Urban / Many markets / commercial activities

3. Methodology of Study

The study location of the road condition covers two segments national road that connects *Yos Sudarso* Port with *Pattimura* Airport in Ambon City, namely segment I or called the down road, and segment II is called the upper road. The two national road segments, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Map of Ambon National Road Segment

The study activities were conducted in a structured and systematic manner in stages according to scientific studies, consists of:

1. Determination aims and objectives to be achieved to provide solutions to the existing conditions of national roads of Ambon City;
2. The literature review is a stage of searching for theory sources appropriate to the study and helps in carrying out various analyzes;
3. The study method is in road border reviewed according to the number of lanes, length of the road, LHR as well as delays and side constraints;
4. Discussion of Ambon national road condition, and
5. Study results and outputs in recommendations to the government.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. The Down National Road Segment

Socially, down national segment crosses seaport transportation activities, commerce, traditional markets, terminals, residential areas, and beaches as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Existing Condition of Down Road Segment

The field road condition in Figure 3 indicated that the segment choice starts from Yos Sudarso road, Pala road, Pantai Mardika road, Pantai Batu Merah road, Ongko Liong road, and Sultan Hasanuddin road. The length and number lane of each road in the segment described in Table 3.

Table 3. The Down Segment Road Data

Road Name	Road Length (km)	Number of Paths
<i>Yos Sudarso</i>	0.474	2 lanes, 2 directions
<i>Pala</i>	0.050	2 lanes, 2 directions
<i>Pantai Mardika</i>	0.832	1 lanes, 2 directions
<i>Pantai Batu Merah</i>	0.466	1 lanes, 2 directions
<i>Sultan Hasanuddin</i>	2.359	1 lanes, 2 directions
Total	4.181	

Based on Figure 4 and Table 2, it is known that the total length of Segment I (down road) is 4.181 km consisting of 5 roads, two roads have two lanes, and three roads have one lane, all of them are two-way roads.

As study material for each road section, the existing conditions and number of lanes are broken down according to the down segment as outlined in the LHR table, the discussion each road section is described in Table 4 and Table 5 and Figure 4-7. The location of the Yos Sudarso Road can be shown in Figure 5, and the LHR data section follows the data owned by the Pala Road section, as shown in Table 4. Daily traffic appears to be dominated by class 1 vehicles (motorbikes and the like), followed by class vehicles 3 (minibus) in public transportation form.

Figure 4. Yos Sudarso Road Section

The LHR data *Pala* Road section survey results dated 13-19 November 2019 can be seen in Table 4. Traffic conditions continue from *Yos Sudarso* to the *Pantai Mardika* section. Under these conditions, the *Pala* section LHR data also applies to the LHR data for *Yos Sudarso* and *Pantai Mardika*. Daily traffic (LHR) appears to be dominated by class 1 vehicles (two-wheeled vehicle), followed by class 3 vehicles (mini-bus).

Table 4. Pala Road Section LHR data

Survey Time	Two-Wheeled Vehicle	Cars	Mini-Bus	Micro-Truck	Light-Truck	Heavy-Truck	Non-Motorized Vehicles
13-Nov-2019	395	14	81	7	4	0	19
14-Nov-2019	413	13	64	8	3	0	30
15-Nov-2019	293	17	65	5	1	2	17
16-Nov-2019	299	13	62	5	2	2	17
17-Nov-2019	294	9	63	4	2	2	17
18-Nov-2019	298	10	64	3	2	2	17
19-Nov-2019	288	12	58	5	2	2	16

The location of the *Mardika Beach* section can be shown in Figure 5. The LHR data follows the survey results of the *Pala* section, as shown in Table 4. Daily traffic (LHR) is dominated by class 1 vehicles (motorbikes), followed by class 3 vehicles (minibusses).

Figure 5. Mardika Beach Road Section

The location of the *Batu Merah Beach* section, can be shown in Figure 5, the LHR data, as shown in Table 5. Daily traffic is dominated by class 1 vehicles (motorbikes), followed by class 3 vehicles (minibusses).

Table 5. Batu Merah Beach Road Section LHR data

Survey Time	Two-Wheeled Vehicle	Mini-Bus	Micro-Truck	Non-Motorized Vehicles
13-Nov-2019	50	23	2	3
14-Nov-2019	53	23	1	3
15-Nov-2019	53	23	1	3
16-Nov-2019	53	23	0	2
17-Nov-2019	52	23	1	2
18-Nov-2019	52	23	0	3
19-Nov-2019	54	26	1	2

Figure 6. Batu Merah Beach Road Section

Sultan Hasanuddin road section is a canal of Ongko Liong road, as shown in Figure 8 and LHR data this road section, as shown in Table 4. Daily traffic is dominated by class 1 vehicles (motorbikes), followed by class 3 vehicles (minibusses).

Figure 7. Sultan Hasanuddin (Ongko Liong) Road Section

Following side barriers classification, the down road is included in the very high side obstacle class based on the MKJI 1997. In the *Pantai Mardika* segment, there are commercial activities, traditional markets, and terminals, so the side obstacles are

categorized very high. In addition, trade activities, exchanges, and terminals are also found in the *Pantai Batu Merah* segment.

4.2. The Upper National Road Segment

The upper road segment partially crosses commercial, office, educational, and residential areas. The current field condition of this segment road can be seen in Figure 8. The segment road choice starts from *Pelabuhan* road, which continues to *A.M. Sangaji* road, *Diponegoro* road, *Ahmad Yani* road, *Rijali* road, and *Sudirman* road.

Figure 8. Existing Condition of Upper Road Segment

Road segment length data and number of lanes are respectively of each section road described in Table 6.

Table 6. The Upper Segment Road Data

Road Name	Road Length (km)	Number of Paths
<i>Pelabuhan</i>	0.232	2 lanes, 2 directions
<i>A.M. Sangaji</i>	0.275	2 lanes, 1 directions
<i>Diponegoro</i>	0.620	2 lanes, 2 directions
<i>Ahmad Yani</i>	0.551	2 lanes, 2 directions
<i>Rijali</i>	1.319	2 lanes, 1 directions
<i>Sudirman</i>	2.807	2 lanes, 2 directions
Total	5.804	

The upper road divided into six roads with two lanes. In the classification of conditions based on directions, these six national roads consist of four two-way roads and two one-way roads. Based on Figure 9 and Table 6, it is known that the total length upper road is 5,804 km, longer than 1,623 km from the down road. While the existing national roads in the upper segment, there are still two roads that still need continuous improvement of requirements for fulfillment as national roads.

The existing conditions and road lanes are described according to upper roads, as outlined in the LHR table. The LHR data for each road section are described in Table 6-8 and Figure 10-14, which shows the location of the road section. The survey result of *Pelabuhan* road section LHR data on 13-19 November 19, 2019, can be seen in Table 6, the pattern of continuous traffic (two directions) in this section, but the *A. M. Sangaji* road, the pattern changes to continuous traffic (one direction). Thus the LHR data in Table 6 only applies specifically to the *Pelabuhan* road section. Daily traffic (LHR) of the *Pelabuhan* road section is dominated by class 1 vehicles (motorbikes), followed by class 3 vehicles (minibusses).

Therefore, the use of office space and places of worship on this road section causes the behavior of vehicle users to change some of the road functions into a vehicle parking lot, especially during the daytime. A.M. Sangaji borders the Port Road boundary at the fork in Sam Ratulangi.

Table 6. Pelabuhan Road Section LHR data

Survey Time	Two-Wheeled Vehicle	Cars	Mini-Bus	Micro-Truck	Light-Truck	Heavy-Truck	Non-Motorized Vehicles
13-Nov-2019	209	25	24	5	2	6	12
14-Nov-2019	173	20	29	4	2	2	8
15-Nov-2019	197	22	25	6	1	7	12
16-Nov-2019	189	14	23	5	1	6	12
17-Nov-2019	186	20	23	4	0	3	9
18-Nov-2019	155	19	21	4	0	4	9
19-Nov-2019	190	21	21	7	2	7	13

LHR data on *A. M. Sangaji* road section survey results on 13-19 November 2019 can be seen in Table 7, with the pattern of traffic that is not continuous (one direction). Changes in traffic patterns occur starting at the intersection of *A. Y. Patty* road to the *Pelabuhan* road becomes continuous (two directions). Thus the LHR data only applies to *A. M. Sangaji* and does not apply to the *Diponegoro* road section due to different traffic patterns. Road boundaries and changes in traffic patterns between *A. M. Sangaji* in one direction and two directions right at the signaled intersection, the location of changes in direction, and the location of the intersection can be seen in Figure 10. The existence of a signaled intersection makes an alternative national road for upper national roads requiring a longer travel time than down national roads due to delays.

Figure 9. A.M. Sangaji Road Section

Table 7. A.M. Sangaji Road Section LHR data

Survey Time	Two-Wheeled Vehicle	Cars	Mini-Bus	Micro-Truck	Light-Truck	Non-Motorized Vehicles
13-Nov-2019	569	54	79	2	4	18
14-Nov-2019	540	46	89	2	3	18
15-Nov-2019	538	54	84	3	4	17
16-Nov-2019	518	49	83	3	4	16
17-Nov-2019	376	38	56	0	2	12
18-Nov-2019	363	38	57	0	1	18
19-Nov-2019	539	55	88	2	6	17

The *Diponegoro* road section's LHR data can be adjusted to survey results on 13-19 November 2019 for the *Ahmad Yani* road section, which can be seen in Table 8. The traffic pattern on the *Diponegoro* road section is continuous as the *Ahmad Yani* road section, which is both in the upper national road. The LHR data of the *Ahmad Yani* road section also applies to the *Diponegoro* road section but does not apply to the *Rijali* road section because of differences in traffic patterns that are not continuous. The border of the *Diponegoro* road section can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Diponegoro Road Section

The LHR data of Ahmad Yani road section survey results on 13-19 November 2019 can be seen in Table 8, the pattern of continuous traffic (two directions), but the *Rijali* road section changes to a pattern of continuous traffic (one direction). Thus the LHR data in Table 8 also applies to *Ahmad Yani*, but it does not apply to the *Rijali* road section. The office land use in this road section causes the vehicle user behavior to make the road a parking lot, especially during the daytime. The *Ahmad Yani* road section can be seen in Figure 11.

Table 8. Ahmad Yani Road Section LHR data

Survey Time	Two-Wheeled Vehicle	Cars	Mini-Bus	Micro-Truck	Light-Truck	Heavy-Truck	Non-Motorized Vehicles
13-Nov-2019	239	10	41	7	3	3	3
14-Nov-2019	239	10	44	8	3	3	2
15-Nov-2019	236	10	42	7	3	4	3
16-Nov-2019	236	10	40	8	3	3	3
17-Nov-2019	227	10	38	8	3	3	3
18-Nov-2019	248	10	42	7	3	4	2
19-Nov-2019	240	10	41	7	3	4	2

Figure 11. Ahmad Yani Road Section

The traffic pattern of the *Rijali* road section is not continuous (one direction), but the *Sudirman* road section changes into a continuous traffic pattern (two directions). Thus the LHR data for the *Rijali* road section requires a separate survey due to differences in traffic patterns between the two roads border the *Rijali* road section, which can be seen in Figure 12.

The pattern of *Rijali* road section is continuous traffic (two directions) begins at the boundary of the *Tulukabessy* T-junction towards *Batu Merah Dalam* T-junction and continues until the *Merah Putih* Bridge. Changes in traffic patterns (one direction) in the upper national road, starting at the *Tulukabessy* T-junction to *Karang Panjang* T-junction. Thus the LHR data for *Sudirman* on different roads, a separate survey is needed because of differences in traffic patterns between the two roads. The boundary of *Sudirman* with *Rijali* and *Batu Merah Dalam* road section, thus the location of *Sudirman* – *Tulukabessy* intersection, is shown in Figure 13.

Based on the field conditions, the upper national road has public facilities that affect traffic activities on the side, for example, pedestrians or lane crossers, city transportation and bus stop to pick and down passengers, vehicles in and out the yard, and off-street parking. The types of side barriers in some of the segments in the upper national road include high category according to MKJI 1997.

Figure 12. *Rijali* Road Section

Figure 13. *Sudirman* Road Section

5. Conclusion

The study results show that the two national road segments connecting *Yos Sudarso* Port with *Pattimura* Airport in Ambon City have different existing conditions. There are three alternative road access options that can be proposed for use as national roads, as follows:

1. The first alternative, using the national road access down road through six roads: *Yos Sudarso, Pala, Pantai Mardika, Pantai Merah Batu, Ongko Liong, and Sultan Hasanuddin* roads section.
2. The second alternative, using national road access upper road, through *Pelabuhan, A.M Sangadji, Diponegoro, Ahmad Yani, Rijali, and Sudirman* roads section.
3. The third alternative is to use the national road access for the down road segment and the parallel upper road segment for the latest conditions, with recommendations for structuring traffic engineering and handling multiple sections into continuous roads.

Based on the conclusions selected three alternative national road access in Ambon City, the following are technical considerations based on choices. The first choice is the down national road access, improvement of road access through the construction of new roads made by the reclamation of the *Mardika* coastal area starting from the Port of *Yos Sudarso, Pantai Mardika, Pantai Batu Merah*, to crossing under the *Merah-Putih* Bridge. The second choice is upper national road access, replace simple crossroads with non-level crossing buildings or flyover development. Starting from the *Merah-Putih* Bridge across *Sudirman, Rijali, Ahmad Yani, Diponegoro, A.M. Sangaji*, as far as *Yos Sudarso* Port. The third choice is Parallel between the down segment and the upper segment as national road access. It was considered by comparing several roads through law enforcement. To support road capacity and intersections down the national road, vehicle parking on the road in *Yos Sudarso* area, structuring of street vendors, and floating market traders in the *Pantai Mardika* area. Widening *Ongko Liong* section, reducing vehicle travel time becomes shorter. Roads in upper segment need to curb parking of vehicles on the road, particularly areas on *Diponegoro* and *Ahmad Yani* sections. Traffic engineering to divert the road from one to two directions on the *Rijali* section, increase the junction capacity of the *Sudirman-Tulukabessy* section, and increase delays to facilitate movement on the *Rijali* section.

This study needs the support of more specific and detailed reviews. The study considers all technical, economic, social, cultural, and environmental conditions around national roads for both existing road segments. Thus the whole picture can be obtained and updated. Current recommendations (temporarily) use the third alternative to become a national road while awaiting specific studies for the use of the first or second alternative.

Acknowledgments

Our appreciation is thanks to Mr. Jhon Sudiman Damanik, Head of the Ambon XVI National Road Implementation Center, for his direction and advice during the study.

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